

THE ISSUES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

Saparov Abat Tursinbaevich

Assistant teacher at the Department of Preschool Education and Defectology. NSPI named after
Azhiniyaz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160772>

Abstract. *Preschool education is the initial part of lifelong education. It ensures the formation of a child as a healthy and developed personality, awakens his desire to learn, and prepares him for systematic learning. The article examines the development of the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the modern period.*

Keywords: *preschool education, reformation, continuing education, road map, qualified personnel.*

Reforming the preschool education system and considering preschool education as the main stage of lifelong education in Uzbekistan is considered a priority. In particular, on August 30, 2017, the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan “On measures for the further development of the preschool education system in 2017-2021” defined the concept of work in this area. This places enormous responsibilities and challenges on our educators in this area.

In order for a person to be happy, proper upbringing is necessary. If a child from early childhood thinks about the question “Who do I want to become?”, then it is necessary to put these children’s thoughts in the right direction, which is ensured by the child attending a preschool educational institution. There is no greater happiness for a child and the country in the future than to receive a good education, master a craft and science, and serve the Motherland and one’s people. In one of his speeches, the head of Uzbekistan noted that “by a perfect person, we understand, first of all, educated people with a high intelligence, able to think independently, who can serve as an example for others with their behavior. Once again, the lack of highly skilled, modern, thinking people continues to be a major obstacle to our progress. The search, education, aesthetic education of such personnel, especially young people, is becoming a pressing issue of today,” he emphasized.

Preschool education is the initial part of lifelong education. It ensures the formation of a child as a healthy and developed personality, awakens his desire to learn, and prepares him for systematic learning.

Preschool education up to 6-7 years of age is carried out in state and non-state preschool institutions and in the family. The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for school, to form a child as a healthy, developed, independent person, and to discover his abilities.

The protection of the life and health of children in a preschool educational institution is carried out by medical workers of the preschool educational institution and full-time medical workers, as well as medical workers of health authorities assigned to the preschool educational institution. The procedure and rules for organizing the protection of the life and health of children in a preschool educational institution, the rules for admitting and sending children to a preschool educational institution, requirements for organizing safety in the premises of a preschool educational institution, requirements for organizing fire safety in a preschool educational institution, and requirements for the safety of the territory are regulated by a number of legislative acts.

In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5198 On September 30, 2017 “On measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system” the Ministry of Preschool Education was created in Uzbekistan. Preschool education departments began to function in all regions of the Republic, as well as preschool education departments in districts and cities. Experienced and qualified specialists have been attracted to the central office and territorial departments of the Ministry of Preschool Education.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-3955 on September 30, 2018, “On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system” was adopted. Based on this resolution, the organizational structure of the Ministry of Preschool Education was determined. It included state preschool educational institutions, non-state preschool educational institutions, district and city departments of preschool education, regional departments of preschool education, as well as other organizations. The Institute for Retraining and Advancement was introduced qualifications of managers and specialists of preschool educational institutions, Foundation for the Development of Preschool Education, specialized design and planning institutes. The central apparatus of the Ministry of Preschool Education has been formed. As noted in the decree, a program of additional measures has been defined to further improve the preschool education system, the implementation of which is carried out in stages.

This program is comprehensive; in a short period of time, a number of legal acts in the field of preschool education have been developed. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019 No. PD-4312, the “Concept for the development of the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” was developed. This concept determined the stages of development of preschool education in our republic for the medium and long term. As a result, if in 2016 the coverage of preschool children in preschool educational institutions was 30 percent, then in 2022 in Uzbekistan the coverage of children in preschool education increased by 4.6%. This was reported to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education. According to the information, such results were achieved thanks to the establishment of 1,811 kindergartens in 2022 (219 state, 1,346 family, 169 non-state on a PEI basis, 77 private kindergartens).

The country now has 29,420 preschool educational organizations, of which 6,589 are state and 22,822 non-state (833 private, 20,676 family and 1,313 non-state preschools based on PEI). 2.1 million or 71.8% of the 2.9 million children of preschool age are enrolled in preschool education, of which 647,655 are children aged 6 years.

The total number of managers and teachers working in state and non-state preschool educational organizations is 151,746, of which 51,554 (33.8%) are teachers with higher education.

Currently, there are 13,500 preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan, which include state, non-state and family preschool educational institutions. Despite this, the coverage of children in our state is 40.5 percent.

The Ministry of Early Childhood and School Education, together with the Global Partnership for Education (GPE), UNICEF, national and international partners, has presented a Roadmap for Education Reform for 2023-2026. According to the UNICEF press service, the Roadmap is aimed at accelerating the reform of the education sector in Uzbekistan to ensure equitable access to quality education.

The document defines clear measurable priorities with results and goals until 2026 for the reform of preschool and school education in accordance with the Development Strategy. It is based on principles such as ethics, integrity, anti-corruption, justice and the realization of human rights.

The roadmap not only strengthens coordination among various stakeholders in the education sector, but also helps scale up the most effective solutions.

Currently, to achieve 80% coverage of children from 3 to 6 years old in the field of preschool education, an additional 620 thousand places in preschool institutions will be required.

The development of the Roadmap was due to a lack of coordination between partner organizations. The agreement now brings together 54 partner organizations and provides a clear agenda for education sector reform. Large-scale work is being carried out to increase the enrollment of children in preschool education, introduce modern innovations, new pedagogical and information and communication technologies and advanced methods into the process of education and upbringing, and develop the material and technical base.

Educational programs for preschool education have been developed and put into practice based on foreign experience. Alternative types of preschool education are being developed, and mobile and modular preschool educational institutions are being widely introduced.

Preschool educational organizations are provided with new equipment, toys, educational materials.

In order to ensure high-quality preparation of preschoolers for school, a yearly system of free preparation for school was introduced. It is planned to introduce advanced pedagogical and digital technologies, new alternative forms into the process of training and education in preschool educational organizations.

It is planned to create and practically implement a new generation of educational literature, didactic materials, electronic educational resources for preschool education, and connect preschool educational organizations to a full-fledged broadband Internet network.

As part of the further development of the preschool education system, the following goals have been set:

- increasing the level of preschool education coverage from 62 percent to at least 80 percent;
- bringing the level of coverage of the preschool education system for children aged 6 years to 90 percent in the 2022/2023 academic year, and to 100 percent by the end of the 2024/2025 academic year;
- creation of over seven thousand new non-state preschool educational organizations by attracting private sector funds to the preschool education system;
- raising the quality of education in the preschool education system to a new stage;
- introduction of an improved system of professional training and improving the skills of kindergarten workers;
- advanced training of over 160 thousand teaching staff in 2022-2026;
- improving the processes of preschool education and upbringing based on scientifically based approaches;
- prevention of violations of the law in the preschool education system.

In order to prevent financial offenses and corruption-related facts, a unified information system will be created in the preschool education system.

Implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to radically improve the preschool education system” will increase preschool education to a qualitatively new level in the country, radically improve infrastructure and material and technical equipping preschool institutions.

All this is the basis for the formation of a new generation of a nation that is comprehensively mature at the level of modern civilization.

REFERENCES

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по совершенствованию управления системой дошкольного образования» от 30 сентября 2017 года № УП-5198. Lex.uz
2. Постановлением Президента Республики Узбекистан от 8 мая 2019 года № ПП-4312 разработана «Концепция развития системы дошкольного образования в Республике Узбекистан до 2030 года».
3. Бекимбетова А.А. и др. The Analysis OF Educational Systems In Different Countries. TEST Engineering & Management Preschool Education And Modern Approach Towards It. США 2020. 29358-29364 стр. <http://www.testmagazine.biz/index.php/testmagazine/issue/view/9>
4. Бекимбетова А., Ергалиева Ж. Development of intellectual and cognitive skills in preschool children through improvement of pedagogical potential.
5. Мирзаева Д.Ш., Кенжаева З.Б. Значение использования интерактивных методов в развитии дошкольного образования // Academy, 2020. № 5 (56).
6. Хакимов, С.У. Система дошкольного образования в Республике Узбекистан / С.У. Хакимов. — Текст : электронный // NovaInfo, 2016. — № 44. — С. 308-311. — URL: <https://novainfo.ru/article/5691> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
7. Vasilievna P. N., Amangeldievna B. A., Inkar K. TUTOR'S SUPPORT OF FUTURE TEACHERS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020. – Т. 8. – №. 3. – С. 37.